

Building a data ecosystem for using telecom data to inform the COVID-19 response efforts

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Abstract

Telecom data are critical for understanding population distribution and mobility patterns, which can help inform the COVID-19 response efforts. They are especially useful for resource-constrained countries where data and financial resources for data collection are scarce. These countries often have limited capabilities to handle and analyze telecom data that require specific technologies and computing environments.

In this paper, we discuss the development of a data ecosystem for using telecom data for development and society in the Global South. Key stakeholders, along with their roles and responsibilities, are also described based on our collaboration with ICT regulators, mobile network operators, and other ministries and aid agencies as data consumers over the last eight years. We also showcase a few ongoing projects to support several African countries in producing mobility statistics to inform the COVID-19 response efforts.

Keywords – telecom data; call detail record (CDR) data; data ecosystem; open-source; COVID-19

1 Introduction

The spread of coronavirus disease (COVID-19) poses unprecedented challenges for societies [1]. While contact tracing is significant in the early stages of an outbreak to contain the spread, pandemics can easily overwhelm a contact tracing system. This leads to the need for non-pharmaceutical interventions that are proven to be effective in preventing the spread of COVID-19 [2][3]. This includes social distancing, banning large gatherings, closing schools and non-essential businesses, mobility restrictions, and lockdown of regions and countries [4][5][6].

Timely and reliable population data are critical for decision making, monitoring, and evaluating intervention. Telecom data are passively collected by mobile network operators (MNOs) for billing and network management purposes. It is updated with each network event—a call, an SMS, and data communication, generating highly localized and frequent digital footprints. Given its wide coverage and ubiquitous usage, especially in resource-constrained environments, telecom data are among the most critical data sources for understanding human mobility patterns, which can inform the COVID-19 response efforts across the early and later stages of the pandemic [7].

Telecom data hold significant benefits, particularly in resource-constrained countries where data and financial resources for data collection are scarce. These countries often have limited capabilities to handle and analyze telecom data that require specific technologies and computing environments. In recent years, many studies and development projects have explored the use of telecom data for public benefit. However, there are often cases where these efforts take too long and/or remain unrealized.

Over the past eight years, we have been working with information and communication technology (ICT) regulators in the Global South, and have provided technical support to establish a data ecosystem for generating actionable population statistics. Since the outbreak of COVID-19, we have been supporting several governments to generate aggregated statistics on population distribution and mobility patterns that can be used to inform the COVID-19 response efforts. In this paper, we answer the following questions by showcasing our works and experiences:

- How can we establish a data ecosystem to enable an optimal dataflow for utilizing telecom data for development and society?

^a Spatial Data Commons is a joint effort initiated by a group of researchers and engineers from The University of Tokyo and LocationMind Inc., with expertise in big data analytics, AI, geospatial analysis, GNSS technology, and social surveys and analysis - <https://sdc.csis.u-tokyo.ac.jp/>

- Who are the key stakeholders, and what are their roles and responsibilities in building such a data ecosystem?

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. Section 2 describes a framework for characterizing a data ecosystem. Section 3 summarizes a practical approach to building a data ecosystem by drawing on our experiences broadly in the Global South. Section 4 illustrates ongoing use cases to support the use of telecom data to inform the COVID-19 response efforts. The final section presents the key findings and conclusions.

2. Framework to characterize data ecosystem

This section introduces three actors engaged in a data ecosystem. Then, we describe a framework for characterizing a data ecosystem for using telecom data for development. The framework is structured around five dimensions: data supply, data infrastructure, data demand, data ecosystem governance, and data privacy. It combines the relevant existing frameworks [8] [9] [10][11] and further details and elaborates on additional elements.

2.1 Three actors and their roles

Building a data ecosystem involves three actors: data producers, consumers, and intermediaries [8] [12], [13]. Fig. 1 shows the roles of each actor under a data ecosystem. The data producer is a source of data, and is responsible for its development, maintenance, and control. In our setting, ICT regulators and MNOs are the data producers/processors. The intermediary is an institution that facilitates and liaises with relevant stakeholders to achieve consensus around a specific dataset or information product. It is often associated with support for handling telecom data, such as tools for data preprocessing, quality assurance, and analytics since technologies and knowledge required to create data products for third parties are not necessarily required for ordinary business operations. The intermediary includes aid agencies,

Fig. 1 The roles of three actors engaged in a data ecosystem

academia, NGOs, and the private sector. It can be a group of institutions that jointly facilitate and provide technical support for an activity. Data consumers use data products for intervention, monitoring, and policy design. They use data for advancing policy and practice, and thus, it is rational for public bodies such as regulators to be involved in generating data even beyond their usual operations.

2.2 Data supply

Data supply as a critical dimension is characterized by the process of getting data access for a data ecosystem. This process begins with arriving at a consensus on using telecom data and how the data are managed, processed, and used. The regulator plays a key role in coordinating with MNOs to realize data supply. It also includes data preparation, such as de-identification, extraction from the server of MNOs, and data transfer to the regulator. Telecom data need to be de-identified so that no personally identifiable information is included for developing information products. The key components of data are timestamps and cell tower locations, which are usually managed by different departments. A MNO does not necessarily know which data are necessary for a given purpose. The facilitation and support of the regulator accelerates the data preparation procedure of MNOs.

2.3 System infrastructure

The de-identified data are fed to a system to develop information products. The regulator usually has systems to generate statistical information using telecom data shared by MNOs for monitoring the markets and their performance. Such existing systems mostly run in a virtual environment, which can be a useful infrastructure for developing additional data products. Considering the time and cost constraints, a new independent system is created on the existing virtual environment in the premise of the data producer. Owing to the nature of telecom data, using cloud computing services is not an option, although it can instantly provide a stable computing environment. A complete processing is performed in the premise of the data producer, which means the de-identified raw data are never brought outside the country. This process also includes system deployment for developing descriptive statistics and maps for data quality assurance and information products as actionable statistics.

Infrastructure described here is still in a form of its early stages, and this is the simplest set up as a system that holds and processes data. In the advanced stage, this dimension functions more as an institutional and systematic means for storing, sharing, and consuming data as a public good.

2.4 Data demand

Data demand is characterized by the use of telecom data for advancing policy and practice by the data consumer. A

government is the primary data consumer; it also includes aid agencies and implementing agencies. As they need specific data for solving development issues, the purpose of data use is reflected in the design of algorithms for generating data outputs. For instance, when the National Statistical Office needs data on internal migration, statistics on seasonal mobility patterns will be generated. Data products are sometimes associated with other services for data consumers, such as dashboards.

2.5 Data ecosystem governance

Data ecosystem governance is a framework to realize optimal data access through stakeholder interactions [10]. Sharing the vision of the data ecosystem helps establish a collaborative environment, while each stakeholder understands its roles and responsibilities to maintain the ecosystem. Each stakeholder requires certain capabilities to participate in the data ecosystem, such as having knowledge and skills to maintain the system, ensuring data security and quality, and utilizing data for informing policies.

2.6 Data privacy

Data privacy is part of the most significant dimensions of a data ecosystem. This overlaps with other dimensions but we use an independent section to highlight the significance of this dimension.

Raw telecom data include personally identifiable information such as phone number, international mobile equipment identity^b (IMEI), and international mobile subscriber identity^c (IMSI). Any personally identifiable information should be de-identified before the data are used to develop information products. These identification numbers are irreversibly encrypted by the regulator or MNOs.

The de-identified telecom data are processed in the premise of a regulator by following local regulations and laws. Sometimes, it takes time for a regulator to set up a stable environment with sufficient hardware in developing countries who often have financial constraints. Aid agencies who are willing to support are often unable to purchase such hardware easily due to various reasons. Network and electrical infrastructures are usually unstable. This requires additional efforts for developing algorithms and techniques to complete simple tasks in multiple steps, for example, by splitting data into multiple chunks, processing them separately, and combining the results. In this regard, efforts on various aspects are needed to ensure the data privacy.

^b IMEI is a unique number assigned to every mobile device, including mobile phones and mobile broadband data cards. This number stays with the mobile device over its entire lifetime.

3 Practical approach

This section describes an approach to facilitate the development of a data ecosystem for using telecom data for planning and decision making. This approach has developed through our experiences in Global South^d. It explains how we work with the three actor—the data producer, data consumer, and intermediary—to establish a data ecosystem in four phases.

3.1 Sharing goals and motivations among stakeholders

Building a consensus among stakeholders is critical for developing a data ecosystem. It consists of bilateral and multilateral workshops, consultations, small experiments, and capacity building. The objective of the workshops is to fill knowledge and technology gaps. A series of workshops are convened for data producers and data consumers to share experiences and knowledge on the use of telecom data for planning and policy design. As a part of the workshops, small experiments are demonstrated to show the potential of telecom data if sample data are provided, for example, a comparison between population distribution derived from telecom data and census data. The data producer is usually represented by an ICT regulator who invites MNOs to some of the workshops for demonstrating how their data could benefit society, and to share goals and motivations. Additionally, technical workshops are conducted mainly for the technical staff of the regulator and MNOs. It includes demonstrating the use of open-source technologies for de-identification, and generating statistics and visualizations from telecom data. It helps motivate them and realize their roles and responsibilities in building a data ecosystem. Findings and feedbacks during this phase, including data demand from the data consumer, are incorporated into the design of the data ecosystem structure.

3.2 Set up environment

Owing to the nature of telecom data, the system infrastructure is developed in the premise of a regulator. It enables the regulator to securely and responsibly manage data. The system set up is based on Hadoop—an open-source framework that manages data processing and storage for big data applications in scalable clusters. It gives users more flexibility in collecting, processing, analyzing, and managing massive amounts of telecom data. The system requires five machines: A Windows-based machine is used for data visualization, de-identification process, and as a jump host for virtual private network (VPN) to Hadoop

^c IMSI is a unique number assigned to the subscriber identification module (SIM) card used by a mobile subscriber. It is used to identify the mobile user within the mobile network.

^d It includes Guinea, Liberia, Sierra Leone, Mozambique, Rwanda, The Gambia, Angola, Sri Lanka, and Bangladesh.

cluster. The other four are CentOS computers for Hadoop clusters. The hardware can be either physical or virtual, and the entire set up can be remotely supported.

3.3 Data supply

Data supply requires close communication between the regulator and MNOs. The regulator is usually well positioned to coordinate with the MNOs, where official letters with detailed data specifications are sent to request for cooperation. This process sometimes involves several transactions because of the requested data components. Namely, two key components are requested for human mobility analysis: the timestamp of call detail records and the coordinates of the cell tower location; these components are managed by different departments. Often, there is a time lag between the data updates; the timestamp, which is updated at near-real time, is associated with systematically assigned IDs of cell towers. The geographic coordinates of cell towers are updated sometime after a new cell tower is installed. This causes an imperfect match between the cell tower ID and geographic location—usually, only 70%–80% of cell towers are correctly mapped initially, and location data are updated later to improve the mapping results.

The data provided by a MNO are irreversibly de-identified such that no personally identifiable information is included. Data specification and open-source software for de-identification are provided if necessary. The data are usually provided in a compressed CSV file format. The data transfer protocol between the MNO and regulator is performed via a secure channel, for example, SFTP, VPN, or direct copy, and the data are stored in the server of the regulator to be fed to the Hadoop system.

3.4 Software deployment and development of information products

The proposed system is used for developing information products such as mobility statistics and visualizations based on the data consumer’s demand. Prior to the analysis, data cleaning and data quality assurance are conducted, as telecom data often includes data loss and errors. For instance, the number of records fluctuates because of the data loss from specific cell towers or failures in the data extraction process. Preprocessing and analysis are performed in the premise of the regulator and by a responsible officer. Hence, to enhance their capabilities and ensure that the work will be done efficiently, specific software for preprocessing and developing information products are deployed. Training for using the software is provided to the regulator as well. Computed results are

provided to the data consumer, such as the Ministry of Health, Ministry of Transportation, and the National Statistical Office for planning and policy design.

4 Use cases

This section introduces ongoing cases which include building a data ecosystem to support the use of telecom data and producing actionable mobility statistics to inform the COVID-19 response efforts. We employed methodologies proposed by the World Bank COVID-19 Mobility Task Force [14] to compute aggregated statistics on population distributions and mobility patterns from telecom data. Fig. 2 describes the overall workflow for generating mobility indicators using telecom data.

Fig.2 Overall workflow to produce mobility statistics

4.1 Mozambique

The first COVID-19 case of Mozambique was confirmed on 22 March, 2020. Many Mozambican workers in South Africa started returning to their village homes before the shutdown of South African borders on 27 March. The number of confirmed cases remained low in April, and slowly started increasing thereafter. As of 25 July, the number of confirmed cases has reached 1,690 [15]. Since April, we have been working closely with the Autoridade Reguladora das Comunicações de Moçambique^c (ARECOM), who collaborates with Instituto Nacional de Saúde^f (INS), Programa de Desenvolvimento Espacial^g (PDE), and Maputo Metropolitan Agency. Each agency requests ARECOM to provide specific statistics on population distribution and movements that are used for monitoring, decision making, and evaluation.

Under the COVID-19 pandemic, we have supported them in setting up a system based on open-source frameworks in the premise, and provided technical support to ensure they are capable of processing large-scale data. In addition, we have provided an open-source software from GitHub to generate the necessary statistics for delivering the information product and visualization to the government agencies. The entire support is being provided remotely.

Our collaboration with the regulator started with the World Bank coordination several in 2015. It aimed to broadly

^c ARECOM is the telecommunication regulatory authority of Mozambique. It was formerly called Instituto Nacional de Comunicações de Moçambique (INCM).

^f INS is the National Institute of Health.

^g PDE is the Mozambique Government Spatial Development Program within the Ministry of Transport and Communication.

utilize the telecom data for development, including urban development and public health. A series of workshops have been convened to highlight the importance of telecom data to potential stakeholders. Coordination with the regulator and MNOs for a consensus on the use of telecom data is led by Fundo de Estrada^h and Administração Nacional de Estradasⁱ (ANE) who were keen to use the telecom data for improving their operation. The system developed for this work is being used as the base for setting up an environment for COVID-19 work in Mozambique.

4.2 Guinea

The number of people infected with COVID-19 has increased rapidly in Guinea since the first confirmed case on 13 March, 2020. As of July, the total number of confirmed cases exceeds 6,800 [16]. In response to the COVID-19 pandemic, the government declared a state of emergency in late March. While the state of emergency was extended repeatedly to encourage social distancing measures, mobility restrictions were slowly eased by shortening the night curfew in the capital, Conakry, and gradually permitting international commercial flights in July.

Mobility in Guinea is relatively high. Significant increases in rural-urban migration accelerate urbanization, while a link between rural and urban areas continues to exist. Seasonal migrations occur in the planting and harvest seasons to help their relatives [15], and this has been observed during the COVID-19 pandemic as well.

We started our collaboration on the use of telecom data for COVID-19 with the Autorité de Régulation des Postes et Télécommunications^j (ARPT) since June 2020. We are supporting them to set up a system for analyzing telecom data on their premises and to generate aggregated mobility statistics. The results will be extended to other ministries and agencies to monitor and evaluate the impact of their social distancing policy.

Prior to this engagement, we worked with the ARPT along with the regulators of Sierra Leone and Liberia under an International Telecommunication Union (ITU) project— "Big Data for Development: Preventing the Spread of Epidemics." An integrated system to generate statistics on mobility patterns, including cross-border mobility, was developed using the telecom data of all MNOs in the three countries. This work included capacity building of regulators.

4.3 Anonymous country

This country confirmed its first case in the middle of March, 2020. In response to an increasing number of patients, its government declared a national lockdown two weeks after the first case was confirmed. The government continued

extending nationwide mobility restrictions, which was eased in early June. The restriction was reinstated in certain parts of the country in late June because of a fresh surge in coronavirus cases, while reopening tourism activities to visitors.

Since March, we have been supporting their ICT regulator to generate statistics on population distributions and mobility patterns using telecom data. It includes the mobility pattern of people with higher exposure risks to potential patients. Prior to the outbreak of COVID-19, a simple system infrastructure had already been installed in the premise; it is a part of an ongoing work to build a data ecosystem for using telecom data broadly for development and society. We provided an open-source software to the regulator to assist them in producing mobility statistics using the existing system in a timely and secure manner. These statistics were provided to a health authority to prioritize the quarantine areas. It was also provided to the police authority to establish screening checkpoints for controlling the spread of coronavirus.

Prior to this engagement, we have also been working closely with the regulator since 2018 to promote the Space Inclusion Initiative, in line with the Smart Africa Alliance goals for creating a single digital market. Through this activity, we have been building capacity for the engineers of the regulator, and working toward the establishment of a CDR analytics center to promote geospatial technology for supporting the SDGs.

4.4 The Gambia

Work for The Gambia started differently from our engagement with other countries. When World Health Organization (WHO) announced the COVID-19 outbreak as a pandemic, we were already working on a project on internal migration as part of the World Bank team as consultants. It is an ongoing project and seeks to build capacity for monitoring internal migration using de-identified telecom data. The Gambia Bureau of Statistics (GBoS) and the Gambia Public Utilities Regulatory Authority (PURA) set up a steering committee on big data for development to coordinate and support all activities under this project. All major MNOs in The Gambia are a part of this effort, with the coordination of PURA.

Under the COVID-19 pandemic, the team assists them in generating mobility statistics to support the operation of PURA and GBoS, who are a part of the National Task Force for Emergencies. The team utilizes the developed system infrastructure for an ongoing internal migration project. Currently, the preliminary results are being reviewed by the regulator, and are expected to be utilized for monitoring and policy design.

^h Fundo de Estrada is the Road Fund.

ⁱ ANE is the National Roads Administration.

^j ARPT is the Regulatory Authority for Posts and Telecommunications of Guinea.

5 Key findings and conclusions

This section summarizes the key findings, including technical challenges. We also list further efforts to be made for advancing the developed system to a systematic and institutional pipeline as a sustainable data ecosystem.

5.1 Key findings

- The leadership of an ICT regulator is key to building and managing a data ecosystem in a sustainable and responsible manner. To secure data privacy, the data should be processed in their premise by following the laws and regulations of their country. This is often associated with several technical challenges but is a critical factor for arriving a consensus on using telecom data.
- Suitable hardware infrastructure is a fundamental but difficult component to be procured without financial support. Aid agencies usually cannot purchase such equipment. Complex techniques and multiple steps are required to complete simple tasks without relevant hardware. Such infrastructure with efficient data pipeline is critical to ensure the capabilities to use and analyze the data during natural disasters and epidemics, where timeliness is critical.

5.2 Conclusions

- Closer institutional coordination is required for advancing the developed system into a systematic analytical pipeline. The developed system is in an early stage and is in the simplest set up, which can only store and process telecom data. It still involves several manual processes, such as data transfer to the system through direct copy.
- Further efforts are needed to enhance the flexibility and interoperability of the developed system. The system is based on open-source frameworks and is easily transferable to other countries. It is possible to run software developed by third parties on the system with adjustments.

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Conflicts of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest. The founding sponsors had no role in the design of the study; in the collection, analyses, or interpretation of data; in the writing of the manuscript; and in the decision to publish the results.

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